

Review Paper Study on Design & Analysis of Circular ESR With Varied Zones

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Abstract— Reservoir tanks are widely used for storing water. Water storage is very important as it plays a vital role in everyday life. Storage reservoirs and water tanks are used to store water and liquids like crude oil etc. Overhead tanks are to be constructed for divide water to the people of village or cow town maintaining certain head of water. In this project, a 2 lakh Liters capacity circular overhead tank is chosen for analysis and design of various structural elements of the tank is carried out.

Keywords— Reservoir, Overhead Tank, Analysis, Design

I. INTRODUCTION

Storage reservoirs and overhead tank are used to store water, liquid, petroleum products and similar liquids. These structures are made of masonry, steel, RCC and pre stressed concrete. aside, masonry and steel tanks are used for lower capacities. The amount of steel tanks is high and hence they are rarely used for water tank. RCC tank is high and hence they are rarely used for water storages. RCC tanks are very popular because, besides the construction and designs being easy, they are cheap, monolithic in nature and can be made of water proof.

- To make a study about the design of water tanks
- Design of circular overhead water tank by limit state method.
- Preparing a water tanks design which is economical and safe, providing proper steel reinforcement in concrete and studying its safety according to various codes.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. A.D.V.S. Uma Maheswari, et al 1 As we know from the past, several reinforced concrete elevated water tanks were

Manuscript Received May 5, 2024; Revised 15 May, 2024 and Published on May 30, 2024

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severely damaged or collapsed during earthquakes all around the world. As a result of general findings, the collapse of the raised tank's supporting system is more critical than the other structural sections of the tank.

2. M. Sai Ramya, et al 2 System's life is its elevated water tanks, that are its extremely significant structures. As a outcome of earthquakes, elevated water tanks have been harm and collapsed in the past. Lack of suitable support systems for the water tank and incorrect staging are responsible for the damage.

3. Nanjunda, et al 3 A contribution to the total water tank was subjected to dynamic forces in the present study, which focused on its reactivity. Large water masses at the top of a narrow staging are the most important factor in determining whether an overhead water tank will fail after an earthquake.

4. Nitesh Singh, et al Water tanks are designed to withstand dead load + live load, wind load, and seismic loads, according to IS rules of procedure. Tanks are often planned for wind forces and not even examined for earthquake loads, believing that they will be safe under seismic forces after they are designed for wind forces. However, this is not always the case. A water tank with an H-shaped inlet is studied for Indian circumstances. Due to the fact that wind flows relative to the face of the earth and exerts loads on structures standing on the ground, the wind's effect on elevated structures is quite important

5. Prashant Bansode 5 Structures such as reinforced concrete elevated water tanks are extremely valuable. During and after earthquakes, they are regarded to be essential lifelines. Like an inverted bob, an elevated water tank is composed of an enormous water mass perched on the topmost stage in its design. For the tank to collapse during an earthquake, this is the most important factor to keep in mind.

6. Rupachandra, et al 6 In industries, liquid storage facilities are used to hold chemicals, oil products, and water for public water distribution networks, among other things. The behavior of cylindrical liquid storage tanks under seismic stresses has been examined according to the IS 1893:2002 draft code part 2. Software (STAAD-PRO) based on finite element modeling (FEM) that determine earthquake-induced forces on tank systems.

7. Ranjit Singh Lodhi, et al 7 Every creation comes from the water. Water is essential to daily living. As a home or industrial storage facility, the overhead liquid storage tank is the most efficient. Water tanks can be classified as overhead, on ground, or under, according on where they are located in the structure.

8. Sonali M. Maidankar 8 R.C.C. raised water tanks were severely damaged or collapsed as a result of a few earthquakes accident in India. According to experts, the tank's support system failed due to an earthquake and a badly constructed staging area.

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III. METHODOLOGY

Figure 1: Workflow of Proposed Work

IV. LITERATURE REVIEW

- Elevated circular tanks shall be designed to distribute water to the people of villages or towns.
- Circular shaped Elevated water tanks are economical compare to rectangular or square tanks, as the thickness of wall can be reduced..
- The design results obtained after successful completion were error free and safe..
- In the design M30 grade concrete and Fe 415 steel are used.

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